

Automated Performance Systems and Enforceability of Contracts: The Case of Amazon Web Services and Microsoft Azure

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Abstract

Amazon Web Services (AWS) is currently the largest cloud computing service provider and appears to have established an effective dominance, which together with its main market participant Microsoft Azure, amounts to more than half of the global market. With the introduction of additional services, namely blockchain-as-a-service (BaaS) including Amazon Managed Blockchain (AMB) and its centralised quantum ledger database (QLDB), AWS aims at integrating different distributed ledger technology (DLT) -based network infrastructures into its platform. Here, AWS utilises predominantly open source technologies such as Corda, Hyperledger Fabric and Ethereum. BaaS is expected to experience accelerated growth, in particular in the light of the current crisis and governmental policies stimulating businesses to be run online.

In the first part of the present paper, BaaS is defined as a distinct cloud computing service under the established EU and Swiss legal and regulatory regimes. A specific focus is given to the potential implications of current developments for a regulatory reform in the EU concerning information society service providers. In this context, BaaS in principle would fall under the category of a platform-as-a-service (PaaS) cloud computing application. In addition, BaaS could be interpreted as constituting a subcategory of an infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) cloud computing application, implying that computing power and storage would be distributed among DLT network participants. Nevertheless, the core element of BaaS, i.e. the provision of a network infrastructure predominantly based on DLT, would give rise to

novel questions related to the level of governance and control over the infrastructure, the network's decentralised applications, and more in particular smart contract code -based transaction finality through consensus protocols.

In the second part, legal relationships between different stakeholders, including third party service providers, within the context of BaaS are mapped. Furthermore, from a legal perspective, issues could arise in the context of potential contractual relationships among different actors at different application and protocol layers, whether in their legal capacity as peers to a given DLT network, or as network developers and deployers, alternatively implicating AWS themselves. In addition, questions of causality and peer dependency on the BaaS architecture would imply uncertainty as to the effectiveness of enforcement tools by the state judiciary in favour of, in particular, individual actors in the context of losses suffered as a result of technical shortcomings, i.e. transaction downtime and latency in the course of the performance of an underlying smart contract code.

Thirdly, the authors analyse the potential systemic and aggregated impact of the market dominance of automated performance systems such as AWS and Azure in their provision of services in relation to BaaS and the creation of peer dependency. The deployment of DLT would in principle facilitate varying levels of decentralisation in governance, respectively automation in contractual relationships by means of the integration of smart contract codes, as well as distribution in data transfer and storage. The definition of contractual and tort rights of network peers however, next to the *de jure* and the *de facto*

ability to enforce these rights would increasingly become pivotal for the general uptake and operability of these platforms.

Further, a technical overview and typology of distinct cloud computing services are provided, next to a juxtaposing analysis of deployed DLT network infrastructures based on governance and participation protocols, i.e. public and permissionless, respectively private and permissioned and other forms of (hybrid) architectures.

Subsequently, the paper presents both contractual and tort liability scenarios arising out of the combination of the cloud computing services with either of the described DLT systems. The said scenarios shall then be further subjected to an enforceability examination taking into account both the legal rights and factual criteria for the enforcement of rights against cloud computing service providers. This analysis shall eventually be utilised to provide for a conclusive outlook on the systemic legal implications different stakeholders could be facing in the context of these emerging service platforms.

Keywords – cloud computing; DLT; smart contract codes; enforcement; governance

1 Typology of Cloud Computing Applications

Despite lacking a universally accepted definition, cloud computing in its most basic form could be described as the supply of computing capabilities through a communication link (Weber & Staiger, 2013). More specifically, cloud computing has been coined as a location independent access to computing resources whereby flexibility is provided for by means of allocation of such resources, among others, from a “pool shared as a fungible resource with other customers” (Weber & Staiger, 2014).

Considered from a rather technical perspective, a cloud computing service is seen to encompass certain characteristics among which are following (Sluijs, 2012). These include a) on-demand self-service mechanism allowing the customers to unilaterally access their desired services; b) ensured availability through ubiquitous network access, i.e. virtual web platform, by means of different devices; c) possibility for resource pooling, also known as multi-tenancy, i.e. services offered to multiple parties simultaneously; d) on-demand and on-supply mass customisation of computing power and e) provision of measured services, in principle allowing for transparency

on both of sides of the spectrum, i.e. the provider and the customer.

By measured services it is meant that the resource usage could be tracked by both parties, achieved by means of mechanical adjustment and manipulation of resources embedded in cloud models (Mell & Grance, 2011).

Here, a distinction would need to be made between different types of service providers dependent on their level of involvement in the decision making processes, network control and governance as well as the potential and consequential liability from such actions thereof.

For the purpose of this study, three distinct types of cloud computing applications could be listed.

Infrastructure-as-a-service (IaaS) is defined as a remote computing and storage service with an unlimited data back-up capacity on servers.

Software-as-a-service (SaaS) occurs when cloud computing services would be available without a need for additional software installation, e.g. Google Maps. Platform-as-a-service (PaaS) stands for the provision of remote access to software development platforms without a need for purchase and deployment of the software and hardware “on the ground”. Customers are therefore enabled to develop, run and manage applications without building or maintaining the infrastructure while utilising their own server power, e.g. Microsoft Azure (Weber & Staiger, 2013).

Important to note that depending on a design and a given participation and access protocol set in place, cloud computing could take either forms of private, public, community or hybrid. Different actors are then identified depending upon the assumption of roles, among which are customer, provider, auditor, broker as well as a carrier.

Specific to the scope of the present paper is primarily the identification and definition of scenarios in which contractual, tort, data protection and secondary liabilities could be established in the context of cloud computing service providers and the scale of their involvement in the course of the provision of services in question.

Here, authors’ focus in particular is driven to blockchain-as-a-service (BaaS), whereby despite its structural similarities to the IaaS and PaaS applications, BaaS brings about additional novel angles for analysis in legal discourse with distributed ledger technology (DLT) being inherent and at the core of its operation. The subsequent section will further outline the underlying reasons for distinguishing BaaS from the rest.

1.1 What Makes Blockchain-as-a-Service Distinct?

In short, BaaS would allow customers to use cloud based solutions to develop, host, run, plug in or adopt DLT applications, including but not limited to smart contract codes. The BaaS provider would in general ensure continuity of the services and maintenance of the infrastructure.

Similar to other cloud computing applications, BaaS is provided, based on a service commission or fee, as a result of a contractual arrangement confirmed between the provider and the customer. Generally speaking, the BaaS provider would deploy the essential resources and leverage the infrastructure as well as the technology in order to set up, configure and ensure maintenance of network nodes on behalf of the customer¹.

BaaS in principle could therefore be considered to fall under the category of PaaS application. Alternatively, BaaS could be interpreted as constituting a subcategory of IaaS application, implying that computing power and storage would be distributed among network participants on DLT platforms. Nevertheless, as previously pointed out, the core element of BaaS, namely the provision of a network infrastructure predominantly based on DLT, would make it distinct from the other existing categories. This novel form of service would consequentially give rise to questions in particular related to the level of governance and control over the network infrastructure, the network's (de)centralised applications, and more specifically smart contract code -based transaction finality through consensus protocols.

2 Distributed Ledger Technology (DLT): Decentralisation & Disintermediation in Network Governance & Control

DLT could be defined as a shared ledger of records, distributed among computer nodes outside jurisdictional boundaries, run and maintained based on defined consensus protocols. Every entry, update or transaction to the ledger would be cryptographically signed and authorised prior to its addition to the chain. The algorithmic consensus would represent the agreed-upon true state among all stakeholders, which could either be reached on a system level, alternatively on an individual deal level depending on the type of DLT deployed.

DLT would take various forms dependent on the deployed participation and governance protocols, among which would be the public and permission-less model, in other words blockchain. Here the ledger would essentially operate on the basis of data broadcasting, where data is

broadcasted when shared with every single node on the ledger irrespective of associated interest or stake. DLT could also be designed in a hybrid public and permissioned format, respectively, in a rather stricter sense, in a private and permissioned format.

In addition, from a legal and regulatory compliance perspective, in data propagation, as opposed to data broadcasting, transaction records would only be shared with nodes on a need-to-know basis depending on their stake, which then would enhance privacy and data protection thresholds.

The form a DLT takes would therefore define the scope of read and write privileges and restrictions granted to the network peers and participants.

Notably, the choice of the architectural form of an underlying DLT would also have potential implications directly or indirectly affecting the way in which a smart contract code is defined and operated. A smart contract code is essentially a decentralised application (d-app) which would run on a DLT network which will further be discussed in the subsequent section.

In this context, identify-ability of network peers and participants; the size of a given network and the selection of its participating nodes; particularities of a designated algorithmic consensus mechanism and lastly transparency of the content of the blocks would be among factors worth consideration (Eenmaa-Dimitrieva & Schmidt-Kessen, 2019).

Moreover, in a peer to peer network infrastructure where the element of trust would in principle be lacking, two attributes are considered essential, authentication and authorisation.

In the framework of a smart contract code, automation is seen as an inherent and key feature, whereby pre-defined terms and conditions as well as outcomes between trust-less peers and network participants (who are parties to a given transaction) would in principle be executed without reliance upon intermediation.

As a result, the scope of automation in the performance of a smart contract code would potentially play a significant role from a legal perspective in defining the legality of its usage, and subsequent enforceability, when analysed within the multi-level regulatory system of the EU. Guaranteed performance in the context of a self-executing automated smart contract code therefore does not necessarily equate with contract enforceability in a legal context. In other words, technical enforcement through an algorithmic code cannot be taken as synonymous to legal enforcement.

On the other hand, accountability in DLT network infrastructures would require clarity on the type of deployed governance and entities involved thereof. In

addition, server infrastructure in terms of redundancy and access rights as well as accessibility to source code and the database used all ought to be taken into consideration (Zetsche et al., 2018).

Moreover, the general discussion for a potential pretext for liability within DLT network would require an analysis from different perspectives, including risks related to levels of transparency and cyber vulnerabilities as well to the network's overall operation.

Cyber vulnerabilities could include a risk of data being tampered with, prior to storage on a DLT network, in particular on public permission-less DLTs where the network would generally lack an identity management layer.

In addition, technical attacks, among others, related to the bundling of computational power in order to enable the targeting of multiple nodes simultaneously, are among the known cyber risks. Errors in software code, next to restricted access to the code by a coordinated group of core developers potentially leading to concentrated decision making, are risks related to the operational aspect of these networks in question (Zetsche et al., 2018).

Last but not least, the internal governance of a given DLT network would be closely interlinked with the factual dynamics surrounding its nodes. Disintermediation effectively sets the ground for poly directional relationships to be established among nodes that are connected through a software programme (Paech, 2017). Questions of liability would therefore need to be analysed in parallel with questions of governance and dynamics of authority among different actors in its various layers.

2.1 Multi-layer Stakeholder Dynamics

From a corporate governance perspective, distributed systems generally would lack a hierarchical organisation whereby participants could be linked to one another, such as computer nodes in the case of DLT networks. Nodes would then communicate with one another via a designated consensus process. From a legal standpoint, the connection between computer nodes could possibly be seen to establish a direct link between network participants.

Nevertheless, in a BaaS platform offered by a cloud computing service provider with a central governance, the (contractual and non -contractual) relationships between different actors in different layers of the network may not always been easily identified. Such a multi-layer stakeholder dynamic would certainly pave the way for legal uncertainty as to the existence of intra -network causality between actions and consequences, respectively as to augmenting the risk of peer dependency on the BaaS platform, without necessarily providing for sufficient legal

recourse, in particular concerning the network end customers and users.

Relevantly, as thoroughly argued (Finck, 2019), within the context of, for instance, public permission-less DLT platforms where the definition of roles and responsibilities are rather complicated, there would be uncertainty as to who would be assigned the role of data controller within the definition of the EU's General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).ⁱⁱ Also, whether actors and stakeholders involved in the different layers of a network, such as protocol and application layers, could fall within the definition of joint data controllership.

A data controllerⁱⁱⁱ is categorised as anyone who alone or jointly with others determines the purposes and means of processing of personal data, whereas data processor^{iv} is anyone who, on behalf of a controller, carries out the act of processing^v, described as effectively any digitally performed operation such as storage, dissemination as well as organisation.

The effect of the GDPR and associated legal implications thereof will further be elaborated in the section 3.

2.2 Automation in Contractual Relationships

The advancement of different DLT networks has raised issues not only in terms of compliance with data protection and privacy of natural persons, but also in terms of the enforceability of smart contract codes upon which decentralised applications are built. Data integrity is of primary importance in a network run by distributed computer nodes. Prior to the occurrence of transaction finality, network peers (parties) would require validation of input and output states before entries on the ledger are correctly updated. An algorithmic consensus process would need to be in place in order to confirm that a certain input state for a proposed transaction has not been spent before.

A smart contract^{vi} code could be defined as an algorithmic code (computer script) written and programmed based on a number of pre-defined terms and conditions and oracles. An oracle is an agent or an interface designed to verify external data and real life occurrences. Upon satisfaction of the pre-defined terms and conditions and update of external data through the means of oracles, the algorithmic code would change its state of information and autonomously self-execute the pre-determined outcome.

A smart contract code has been considered as a computerised transaction protocol that executes the terms of a contract^{vii}. As an agent-generated mechanism, a smart

contract code could also be seen to have the capacity to shift rights and obligations (Werbach & Cornell, 2017).

In terms of validity and enforceability of a contractual arrangement, smart contract codes may pose a problem given their inherent automated nature. Needless to say, a smart contract code is effectively considered valid once it is accepted as part of an algorithmic consensus process on a DLT. Once such a process would take place, it is irreversibly (technically) enforced even in cases where it may be considered to have fraudulently been induced (Werbach & Cornell, 2017).

As pointed out previously, a smart contract code could integrate contractual obligations, in particular on different layers of DLT, namely in the form of network, application and/or basic level contracts.

On a network level, a distinction is made as to whether the network's protocol is offered on an open source basis, alternatively on a proprietary basis with a defined provider. In the case of former a direct contractual link between the developer(s) of the protocol and network participants may not be established easily (Furrer, 2018).

On an application level, on the other hand, network participants and the developer (s) of the application running on the DLT could in principle have a direct contractual relationship for the provision of a given software application as a service. Lastly, on a basic level, network participants would agree among themselves on mutual rights and obligations.

It is argued that whether a legal claim could be established in favour of network participants against respective provider(s) would mainly depend on the existence of a contractual relationship in the first place (Furrer, 2018).

3 Contractual (& Tort) Rights & Claims of Network Participants

Within the EU legal and regulatory context, a first question bearing significance would be whether a cloud computing service provider would in principle fall under the definition of an Information Society Service (ISS), as stipulated by the Information Society services Directive^{viii}. An ISS would refer to any service provided by electronic means for remuneration, at individual request of a recipient of services. Authors take the view that a cloud computing service provider would in theory qualify as an ISS.

The EU e-Commerce Directive^{ix} is designed to cover service providers qualifying as ISS, providing for an effective exemption from liability regime. In a rather narrower scale, it is designed to regulate responsibilities of Internet Service Providers (ISPs) and allot exemptions from liability concerning all types of activities initiated by

third parties, set in Articles 12 to 14, for three distinct types of services under certain conditions, namely the provision of mere conduit, caching and hosting.

Arguably, a cloud computing service provider may not qualify as either a mere access provider, alternatively a host provider, in order to be considered eligible for the exemptions set down in the e-Commerce Directive. Newly emerging types of service providers, often combining different services together, has also increasingly made it complicated to categorise these providers, e.g. the concept of cloud hosting whereby cloud computing and hosting services have seemingly merged to constitute an entirely new product (Weber & Staiger, 2014).

In this regard, as previously mentioned, the location independent characteristic of cloud computing services would inevitably make them distinct from the provision of host services.

Generally, for a liability claim to have sufficient merits and standing a number of criteria would require to be met. As well noted by Weber & Staiger, these include, among others, a) the existence of a quantifiable damage; b) a compromising act on the side of the cloud computing service provider; c) causality between the act in question and the incurred damages and d) lack of performance as a breach of contract. Moreover, the definition of applicable laws in the absence of any contractual 'choice of law' clause would be decisive.

Notably, contractual clauses and disclaimers limiting or even excluding liability in favour of cloud computing service providers could inevitably reduce end customers' bargaining power, hence negatively affecting enforceability of network participants' rights and claims. The standard contractual terms and clauses (SCCs) of the cloud computing market dominant players, namely Amazon and Microsoft, confirm inclusion of broad liability exclusion clauses.

As referred to, civil liability may be derived from a contractual relationship between the cloud computing service provider and the customer. Contract law is therefore seen as "the basis for regulating server availability, consequences of (direct and indirect) losses caused by server downtime as well as any disaster recovery and back-up strategy. The rights and obligations of either party would depend on the type of contract used and the terms incorporated" (Weber & Staiger, 2014).

Furthermore, a tort claim could in principle have merits, albeit more onerous to prove in comparison with the claims of breach of contract, provided that a duty of care in favour of the customers and an associated negligence on the side of the cloud computing service provider(s) could be

established. Here the proof of existence of the element of causality, in the context of the incurred damages, would be decisive.

Finally, given the borderless nature of cloud computing services as well as DLT network infrastructures, with latter having computer nodes distributed cross jurisdictions, compliance with the EU data protection laws would prove burdensome. It is noted that the data protection regime mandated by the GDPR has been foreseen to be interpreted in accordance^x with the liability regime of the e-Commerce Directive.

3.1 Personal Data Perspective under the EU Privacy Regime

Data subjects suffering material or immaterial damage as a result of an infringement of their rights under the GDPR are in a position to claim compensation. In allocating liability to data controllers and data processors, as referred to previously, multiple parties can become implicated. Due to the nature of cloud computing, a clear designation of parties acting as either controller or processor may not always be straightforward, as account needs to be taken of any party involved in the contracting and subcontracting of a variety of services, often involving different jurisdictions.

In a DLT context, the European Parliament (EP) in a recent study^{xi} reiterated that many actors could qualify as joint-controllers as per Article 26 GDPR.

In case of a multi-layered DLT network, an actor could qualify as a controller, when seen to influence or determine the purpose and means of personal data processing at the application layer. In a private DLT, on the other hand, there is generally an entity determining the means and often the purposes of the personally identifiable data (PII) processing, which would qualify it as the controller, with other parties, such as those using the DLT infrastructure, potentially qualifying as joint-controllers.

Infringements under GDPR centre around rights related to PII^{xii}, defined as any data relating to an identified or identifiable natural person or data subject. An identifiable natural person is one who can be identified, directly or indirectly, in particular by reference to an identifier such as a name, an identification number, location data, an online identifier, next to other determinants.

Data controllers are also subject to the principle of accountability^{xiii} and are required to ensure comprehensive ex ante and ex post discipline over data processing including the implementation of appropriate technical and organisational measures such as encryption or pseudonymisation, referred to in Article 6(4)(e). Introduced by GDPR into the legal framework of the EU,

pseudonymity^{xiv} stands for technical detachment of data from direct identifiers whereby in the absence of any additional information, link-ability and attribution of data to a data subject would in principle become impossible, while preserving data utility. Anonymous^{xv} data and processing thereof has therefore been explicitly left outside the scope of the Regulation.

In order to comply with data protection and privacy requirements, as reiterated previously, data would require to be anonymised at source prior to it being made available, which would in turn impede with the link-ability of datasets (D'Acquisto, 2015). It is important to take notice that personal data would need to be encrypted both at rest, while stored, and in transit, while being transferred, to ensure effective compliance with the data protection regime (Compagnucci, 2019).

Nevertheless, it is notable that the process of de-identification and depersonalisation of data repositories in order to anonymise personal datasets, for privacy and data protection grounds, from a technical perspective, is not an absolute tool. Reaffirmed by a new study, carried out by means of a designed generative graphical tool, the likelihood of correct re-identification (singling out) of a data subject was estimated even in heavily incomplete datasets. The results are disturbing, rendering the anonymity threshold set forth by GDPR complicated to achieve (Rocher et al., 2019).

This in turn would have repercussions from a legal perspective, where data subjects are given the right to erasure of their personal data, under Article 17 GDPR^{xvi} albeit not in an absolute sense.

Contractual terms for processing would usually define purpose and duration, the nature of any personal data processed, as well the different data subject classes and the obligations and rights of the controller, keeping in mind, under the GDPR, the assistance processors would need to provide to controllers in latter's fulfillment of complying with requests from data subjects exercising their rights. In addition, contracts would state confidentiality and the need for appropriate measures to enable security, defining that processors can only process and transfer personal data to a third country or multinational organisation, upon a documented instruction from controller.

A recent decision by the Court of Justice of the European Union (CJEU)^{xvii} invalidated the EU-US Privacy Shield agreement on data sharing and data transfers outside the EU or European Economic Area (EEA) or third countries. The Privacy Shield, operational since 2016, was aimed to protect the fundamental rights of data subjects in the EU, whose personal data was transferred for commercial purposes to companies certified in the United States.

Central to the case at the CJEU, however, was the reaffirmation of the use of SCCs. In the absence of an adequacy decision, Article 46 GDPR deals with the “appropriate safeguards” required for controllers to transfer PII to third countries, such as through the adoption of SCCs.

The European Commission (EC) has so far issued two sets of SCCs for data transfers from data controllers in the EU to data controllers, respectively a set to processors, established in third countries. Controllers and processors are encouraged to provide additional safeguards via contractual commitments that supplement SCCs.

Next to SCCs, Binding Corporate Rules (BCRs) which need to be approved by a competent supervisory authority are alternative safeguards that could be utilised as a method for transferring personal data under Article 46 GDPR. BCRs expressly need to confer enforceable rights on data subjects with regard to the processing of their personal data, respecting the application of the GDPR principles, in particular purpose limitation, data minimisation, limited storage periods, data quality, data protection by design and by default, existence of a legal basis for processing, processing of special categories of personal data, measures to ensure data security, and the requirements in respect of onward transfers to bodies not bound by the BCRs .

In order to determine the role of AWS or Microsoft Azure as potential joint-controllers or processors of PII, authors take the view that such criteria would need to be defined in the context of the technologies used.

From the information available publicly, AWS seem to apply SCCs, allowing controllers to transfer PII from the EU and the EEA countries to third countries. AWS claims to be able to provide the same level of protection to data subjects as in the EU.

With regards to the provision of its BaaS services, AWS describes it as one “addressing market needs”, whereby hardware and software is configured for its users, in addition to the setting up of networking and security components. The service also provides for voting API, whereby users can vote to add or remove users, enabling a certain level of governance. Furthermore, the AWS Amazon Managed Blockchain (AMB) is designed to monitor the performance of blockchain networks and can automatically replace poorly performing nodes in order to ensure scalability, as the usage of applications on the network increases. In addition, the AWS AMB also provides for key management service technology which is set to eliminate the need for network operators (and participants) to install separate key storage mechanisms.

According to case law of the CJEU^{xviii}, a mere influence over the purpose and means of processing of PII, would qualify an actor as a controller, whereby joint responsibility of several actors for the same processing does not require each of them to have access to the PII concerned.

The existence of joint responsibility does not necessarily imply equal responsibility of the various operators engaged in the processing of personal data. The level of liability for these operators must be assessed in each case, as operators may be involved at different stages of that processing of personal and to different degrees.

In addition, in case computer nodes, that store a full or partial copy of a DLT, would participate in the validation of new blocks, it could be argued that they would qualify as joint-controllers.

The extend the CJEU decision will have an impact on the operations of BaaS and the contractual relations between the different actors would depend on the type of DLT deployed, taking account of the different applications and protocol layers of the distributed and disintermediated technology and its suitability to provide the required assurance of equivalent levels of data protection. Here, according to the CJEU, relying on a SCC, the data controller would need to provide assurance that, prior to transferring data to the USA, equivalent levels of protection as within the EU would need to be afforded to data subjects.

It is clear however that assurance of equivalent levels of data protection in a DLT context would only be secured in case PII would be self-sovereign, or under the exclusive control of the data subject.

In the case of public permissionless DLT, its distributed architecture means that each full node processing and validating transactions would necessarily have access to any PII, albeit in a pseudonymous format. Due to its public nature, pseudonymity in this instance seems no longer secured through a technical detachment of data from direct identifiers as with any additional information, link-ability and attribution of data to a data subject would now in theory become possible. In addition, the immutability of DLT would then serve to enhance attribution.

This would go against the GDPR principle of data protection by design and by default as well as measures to ensure data security, hence a potential nonalignment with the requirement of providing appropriate safeguards under Article 46, referred to earlier, and the assurance a data controller would require to provide relying on the use of SCCs or BCRs.

Considering the distributed nature of nodes on DLT networks, it seems inevitable that public DLT would therefore be incompatible with these requirements.

4 Concluding Remarks

With increasing prevalence of emerging data-driven provision of services provided for by market dominant actors in cloud computing industry such as AWS and Microsoft Azure, power dynamics are constantly being put in flux between different actors and stakeholders, in particular in differing levels in the context of network infrastructures where DLT is deployed as a foundation. As a consequence, individuals' or end-customers' rights risk increasingly being obfuscated and impaired.

The present paper provided for a descriptive and analytic legal analysis as to the implications of deploying the BaaS application by centrally governed cloud computing service providers such as AWS and Microsoft Azure, under the light of emerging multi-layer stakeholder dynamics, automated contractual relationships, and enforceability of rights thereof.

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ⁱ With reference to <https://www.leewayhertz.com/guide-to-blockchain-as-a-service/>

ⁱⁱ Regulation (EU) 2016/679

ⁱⁱⁱ GDPR Article 4(7)

^{iv} GDPR, Article 4(8)

^v GDPR, Article 4(2)

^{vi} Technical definition to be distinguished from a contract definition in a legal context

^{vii} Szabo Nick, 1994

^{viii} Information Society services Directive (EU) 2015/1535, Article 1

^{ix} Electronic Commerce Directive 2000/31/EC, Articles 12 - 14

^x GDPR, Article 2(4) and Recital 21

^{xi} European Parliament 2019. *Blockchain and the General Data Protection Regulation: Can distributed ledgers be squared with European data protection law?* EPRS. With reference to [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EP_RS_STU\(2019\)634445_EN.pdf](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/STUD/2019/634445/EP_RS_STU(2019)634445_EN.pdf)

^{xii} GDPR, Article 4(1)

^{xiii} GDPR, Article 24

^{xiv} GDPR, Article 4(5) and Recital 28

^{xv} GDPR, Recital 26

^{xvi} With reference to Recitals 65 and 66

^{xvii} Case C-311/18, Judgement of the Grand Chamber; 16 July 2020 (Schrems II)

^{xviii} Case C-40/17, Case C-210/16, Case C-25/17